

THE BENEFITS OF USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH

Durova Shakhnoza Shokirovna

Asia International University

Department of history and philology

Email: shahnozdurova@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This article discusses modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and the possibility of their use in teaching and learning foreign languages.*

Key words: *computer, communication tools, platforms, online resources, websites, educational materials.*

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ И ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются современные информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ) и возможности их использования в преподавании и изучении иностранных языков.*

Ключевые слова: *компьютер, средства коммуникации, платформы, онлайн-ресурсы, веб-сайты, учебные материалы.*

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, great attention is paid to effective use of ICT in learning and teaching foreign languages. For this reason, a different approach to the process of teaching the young generation is required. The role of the teacher in the lessons is also changing. The teacher now acts mainly as a guide. It is time for teachers who aim to keep pace with the times to be ready to enliven any part of the lesson through ICT.

THE ROLE OF ICT IN TEACHING ENGLISH

In fact, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, in the purposeful organization of game-based lessons that are interesting to students, is very large. ICT is becoming an integral part of the educational process. In order to teach young people English through a computer a teacher must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. It also includes the ability to organize new educational programs based on it. In order to become a pedagogue of this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work more on himself in the field of modern technologies. Computer-based English language teaching has several advantages compared to traditional teaching methods. First of all, a computer-based English language learner has four areas of language skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will be able to test their skills. Currently, this is possible with the help of advanced programs. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education.

Online resources, platforms and software increasingly, English as a Second Language (ESL) learners are now learning and they have access to many resources that facilitate practice. This article we various advantages of information technologies in learning English, to educational

materials from improving access to enhancing communication and collaboration in language learning we will discuss. Based on the advantages of IT in learning English to its students ability to provide access to a wide range of educational materials. Traditional methods of language learning, such as textbooks and classroom lectures, take time and limited due to cost constraints. However, with the development of IT platforms for language learning, students can practice their language skills. variety of authentic texts, audio and video recordings, as well as interactive exercises and they can use quizzes. Examples include Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone websites provide students with everything from grammar exercises to online quizzes and language provides an opportunity to use a wide range of language resources up to games. Such resources for English language learners' reading, writing, speaking and listening skills are invaluable in teaching.

Another advantage of IT in language learning is that it is for English language learners using materials that match their personal needs and interests allows. Different people have different interests and learning styles and are traditional educational resources may not always meet these specific needs. However, online platforms that match individual students' interests and learning styles able to provide specially tailored resources. For example, to finance or medicine the interested English language learner more specialized vocabulary in their areas of interest magazines, articles and podcasts on such topics to help you create can use real sources like This customized approach facilitates more effective learning and keeps students motivated and engaged in the long run helps to be.

Another important advantage of IT in language learning is communication between students and is the ability to strengthen cooperation. Learning a language requires a lot of communication practice and IT helps facilitate this through online forums and chat rooms, here students can communicate with each other in a supportive community. Using social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, as well as English learners with other learners around the world helps to connect and practice communication in English.

The use of ICT allows you to effectively solve subsequent didactic tasks in learning English:

- developing skills and abilities to read foreign texts;
- improving auditing skills;
- improving reading skills;
- improving the skills of constructing monologue and dialogic statements;
- improving writing skills when compiling various types of abstracts, retellings, reports;
- replenishment of vocabulary with modern vocabulary foreign language;
- formation of sustainable motivation for foreign language activities.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, multimedia products can be a powerful motivational factor and attract people to learn. At the same time, the role of the teacher will not become less significant. No amount of the latest technology can replace a teacher in the classroom.

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